

Ho³⁺-PVC membrane potentiometric electrochemical sensor based on 2-acetylfurane thiosemicarbazone as an ionophore

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Abstract : A highly selective and sensitive plasticized membrane sensor for holmium(III) ions, based on 2-acetylfurane thiosemicarbazone (AFT) as membrane carrier, was prepared. The sensor shows a linear dynamic range of 1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-2} M, with a Nernstian slope of 19.8 ± 0.3 mV per decade, and a detection limit of 5.5×10^{-7} M. It has a fast response time of ~ 5 s and could be used in a pH range of 2.3–7.8. The proposed sensor revealed very good selectivities with respect to most of the common metal ions including Yb, Sm, Pr, Gd, Er, Tm, Cr, Fe, Na, K, Ca, Cd, Ni and Pb ions. The practical utility of the sensor has been demonstrated by using it as an indicator electrode in the potentiometric titration of Ho^{III} with EDTA, determination of fluoride ions in two mouth wash preparations and also to the determination of Ho^{III} ions in tap water and river water samples.

Keywords : Potentiometry, ion-selective electrode, PVC membrane, sensor.

Introduction

Holmium is one of the rare earths that can be found in equipment such as color televisions, fluorescent lamps, energy-saving lamps and glasses. It is also capable of absorbing fission-bred neutrons; therefore, it is used in nuclear reactors to control atomic chain reactions. All holmium compounds should be regarded as highly toxic, although initial information suggests that the danger is limited. Many techniques have been developed in order to determine the value of Ho^{III} in real samples such as : inductively coupled plasma atomic mass spectroscopy (ICP-AMS), inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES), isotope dilution mass spectrometry, ⁷ neutron activation analysis, X-ray fluorescence spectrometry, etc. These methods are either time consuming, involving multiple sample manipulations, or too expensive for most analytical laboratories. In recent decades, many intensive studies on the design and synthesis of highly selective ionophores as sensory molecules for ion-selective electrodes (ISEs) have been reported. Potentiometric detection based on ISEs, as a simple method, offers several advantages such as speed and ease of preparation and procedures, simple instrumentation, relatively

fast response, wide dynamic range, reasonable selectivity, and low cost. These characteristics have inevitably led to sensors for several ionic species, and the list of available electrodes has grown substantially over the last few years¹⁻⁴. In recent years, we reported some highly selective and sensitive sensors for metal ions⁵⁻²⁵. In this work, we wish to report the fabrication of a highly selective and sensitive Ho^{III} membrane sensor based on 2-acetylfurane thiosemicarbazone (AFT) (Fig. 1) for the monitoring of Ho^{III} ion concentration in real samples.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of AFT.

Experimental

Reagents :

Reagent grade acetophenone (AP), benzyl acetate (BA), dibutyl phthalate (DBP), nitrobenzene (NB), tetrahydro-

THF), sodium tetraphenylborate (NaTPB), high relative molecular weight PVC and nitrate and chloride salts of all cations were purchased from Merck Chemical and Aldrich Co. and used as received. The ionophore 2-acetyl furane thiosemicarbazone (AFT) was prepared as formerly described²⁶. During the experiments, doubly distilled deionized water was used.

Preparation of the electrode :

The PVC membrane preparation involved the blending of the following compounds; 30 mg of powdered PVC, 56 mg of the NB plasticizer, 2 mg of the AFT ionophore, 2 mg of the NaTPB and 10 mg of the OA additives in 5 mL of fresh THF. The resulting mixture was transferred into a glass dish (2 cm in diameter) and the solvent was evaporated slowly until an oily concentrated mixture was obtained. A Pyrex tube (3–5 mm i.d.) was dipped into the mixture for about 10 s, so that a transparent membrane of about 0.3 mm in thickness was formed. The tube was, then, removed from the mixture, kept at room temperature for about 24 h and filled with an internal filling solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ of HoCl_3)^{27–36}. The electrode was finally conditioned for 24 h by soaking in a $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ holmium chloride. A silver/silver chloride electrode was used as an internal reference electrode.

The EMF measurements :

All electromotive force (EMF) measurements were carried out with the following cell assembly :

$\text{Ag-AgCl} \mid \text{internal solution, } 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M \text{ HoCl}_3 \mid \text{PVC membrane} \mid \text{sample solution} \mid \text{Hg-Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{KCl (satd.)}$

A Corning ion analyzer with a 250 pH/mV meter was used for the potential measurements at 25.0 ± 0.1 °C. The activities were calculated according to the Debye-Huckel procedure³⁷.

Results and discussion

Ho³⁺ sensor potential response :

Some neutral ion carriers containing nitrogen and sulfur donor atoms have lately been applied to the construction of highly selective transition and heavy metal ion membrane sensors. Considering the existence of three nitrogen donor atoms in the structure of AFT, it was expected to act as a suitable ion carrier for special transition and heavy metal ions (higher charge density) in the PVC membranes. In order to check the selectivity and

the suitability of AFT as an ion carrier for Ho^{3+} and other metal ions, the ionophore AFT was used as a neutral carrier in the construction of membrane sensors for a wide variety of cations including alkali, alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions. For all these ions, except for the Ho^{III} ion, the slope of the corresponding potential pM plots was much lower than the expected Nernstian slopes of 59, 29.5 and 20 mV per decade, for the uni-, di- and trivalent cations, respectively. This observation is most probably due to the proper size of Ho^{III} ion to the semi cavity of flexible AFT, and the rapid exchange kinetics of the resulting AFT- Ho^{III} complex.

The influence of membrane composition :

It is well understood that the sensitivity, linear dynamic range, and selectivity of the ISEs depend not only on the nature and amount of the ionophore used, but also significantly on the properties of plasticizer, plasticizer/PVC ratio, and, especially, the nature and the amount of the additives employed^{38–46}. The performance characteristics of several membranes, having ingredients of different proportions, are listed in Table 1. It is seen that the membrane number 8 with the PVC : NB : AFT : OA : NaTPB ratio of 30 : 56 : 2.10 : 2 exhibits a Nernstian slope over a broad Ho^{III} ion concentration range. As is seen from Table 1, among the four different plasticizers used, NB resulted in the best sensitivity. This phenomenon can be due to the dielectric constant of the plasticizer on membrane phase.

Moreover, it is interesting to note that the lipophilic negatively or positively charged additives improves the potentiometric behavior of certain ion-selective electrodes by reducing the ohmic resistance and improving the response behavior and selectivity and, in some cases, by catalyzing the exchange kinetics at the sample-membrane interface. The data given in Table 1 showed that in the absence of a proper additive, the sensitivity of the PVC-membrane based on AFT was low (no. 1 with a slope of 12.4 ± 0.2 mV per decade). However, the presence of 2% NaTPB and 10% OA as a suitable lipophilic additives improved the sensitivity of the Ho^{3+} sensor considerably (no. 8 with a slope 19.8 ± 0.3 mV per decade).

Calibration graph :

The EMF response of the PVC membrane at varying concentrations of holmium ions (Fig. 2) indicates a recti-

Table 1. Composition of membrane ingredients

Membrane No.	Composition (wt. %)				Slope (mV/decade)	Concentration range (M)
	PVC	Plasticizer	Additive	AFT		
1	30	NB, 68	NaTPB, 0	2	12.4 ± 0.2	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
2	30	NB, 67	NaTPB, 1	2	16.2 ± 0.4	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
3	30	NB, 66	NaTPB, 2	2	18.2 ± 0.6	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
4	30	NB, 65	NaTPB, 3	2	16.8 ± 0.3	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
5	30	NB, 57	NaTPB, 2; OA, 10	1	17.5 ± 0.5	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ – 5.0 × 10 ⁻²
6	30	NB, 55	NaTPB, 2; OA, 10	3	18.7 ± 0.3	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
7	30	NB, 61	NaTPB, 2; OA, 5	2	18.6 ± 0.4	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
8	30	NB, 56	NaTPB, 2; OA, 10	2	19.8 ± 0.3	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
9	30	AP, 66	NaTPB, 2	2	15.8 ± 0.3	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
10	30	BA, 66	NaTPB, 2	2	14.2 ± 0.6	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
11	30	DBP, 66	NaTPB, 2	2	14.5 ± 0.5	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ – 1.0 × 10 ⁻²

Fig. 2. Calibration curve of the holmium sensor based on AFT.

linear range from 1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-2} M. The slope of the calibration curve was 19.8 ± 0.3 mV per decade of Ho³⁺ ions activity. The detection limit, as determined from the intersection of the two extrapolated segments of the calibration curve, was 5.5×10^{-7} M.

pH effect :

The pH response profile for the electrode was examined by using 1.0×10^{-3} M of HoCl₃ solution over the pH range of 1.0–10.0 and the results are shown in Fig. 3. The pH was adjusted by introducing small drops of concentrated nitric acid or sodium hydroxide. As it is seen, the potential remained constants from pH 2.3 to 7.8, beyond which a drift in potential was observed. The observed drift at higher pH values could be due to the formation of some hydroxyl complexes of Ho^{III} solution. At lower pH than 2.3, the nitrogen atoms in the structure of

Fig. 3. The pH effect of the test solution (1.0×10^{-3} M) on the potential response of the holmium sensor.

ionophore can be protonated and the potential increased.

Dynamic response time :

It is well known that the dynamic response time of a sensor is one of the most important factors in its evaluation. In order to measure the dynamic response time of the proposed sensor the Ho³⁺ concentration of the test solution was successively changed in a concentration range of 1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-2} M in a stepwise manner, and the potential versus potential behavior was recorded and the resulting data depicted in Fig. 4. The response time of the membrane electrode thus obtained was ~ 5 s over the entire concentration range.

Selectivity coefficients of the Ho³⁺ electrode :

Potentiometric selectivity coefficients, describing the preference of the AFT-based membrane sensor for an interfering ion, B, relative to holmium ions, A, were

Fig. 4. Dynamic response time of the holmium sensor for step changes in the Ho^{3+} concentration : (A) $1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, (B) $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, (C) $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, (D) $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, (E) $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$.

determined by the matched potential method⁴⁷⁻⁵¹. According to this method, the specified activity (concentration) of the primary ion (A) is added to a reference solution, and the potential is measured. In a separate experiment interfering ion (B) are successively added to an identical reference solution, until the measured potential matched that obtained before the addition of the primary ions. The matched potential method selectivity coefficients are then given by the resulting primary ion to interfering ion activity (concentration) ratio, $K^{\text{MPM}} = \Delta a_A/a_B$. The resulting selectivity coefficients values are given in Table 2. From the data given in Table 2, the selectivity data indicates that for all diverse cations used, the K^{MPM} values are in the order of 4.3×10^{-3} or smaller and it is immediately obvious that the proposed Ho^{III} sensor is highly selective with respect to most of cations.

Table 3 compared the performance characteristics of the proposed sensor with those of the best previously reported holmium sensors. It is immediately obvious, not only the working concentration range and detection limit

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients of the developed Ho^{3+} electrode

Ion	K^{MPM}
Yb^{3+}	1.0×10^{-4}
Sm^{3+}	2.2×10^{-3}
Pr^{3+}	3.6×10^{-3}
Gd^{3+}	4.2×10^{-3}
Er^{3+}	6.5×10^{-4}
Tm^{3+}	3.0×10^{-4}
Cr^{3+}	4.3×10^{-3}
Fe^{3+}	2.7×10^{-3}
Ca^{2+}	8.3×10^{-4}
Na^+	4.8×10^{-4}
K^+	7.2×10^{-4}
Ni^{2+}	1.0×10^{-4}
Cd^{2+}	8.5×10^{-4}
Pb^{2+}	4.5×10^{-4}

of proposed sensor, but also its selectivity coefficients are superior to those reported for the holmium ion-selective membrane electrodes⁵²⁻⁵⁷.

Analytical application :

The suggested Ho^{III} PVC-membrane sensor was found to work well under the laboratory conditions. The selective holmium membrane sensor was used as an indicator electrode in the titration of a $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ holmium ion solution with a standard $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ EDTA. The resulting titration curve is shown in Fig. 5. According to this figure, the sensor is capable of monitoring the amount of holmium ions.

The proposed sensor was also successfully applied to the determination of fluoride ions in two different pharmaceutical preparations. 1.0 g of each sample was taken and diluted with distilled water in a 100 ml flask and

Table 3. Comparison of selectivity coefficients, detection limit, slope, pH range, response time and linearity range of the developed Ho^{3+} sensor and the formerly mentioned Ho^{3+} ion-selective electrodes

Parameter	Ref. 52	Ref. 53	Ref. 54	Ref. 55	Ref. 56	Ref. 57	This work
L.R. (M)	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.0 \times 10^{-1}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-5} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-5} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$	$2.0 \times 10^{-5} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$
D.L. (M)	6.3×10^{-7}	7.5×10^{-7}	7.0×10^{-6}	8.0×10^{-6}	8.5×10^{-6}	5.0×10^{-6}	5.5×10^{-7}
Response time (s)	10	15	<15	5	<15	<10	~5
pH range	4.5-9.0	3.8-8.0	4.0-9.5	3.0-11.5	2.7-9.8	2.5-10.5	2.3-7.8
Slope (mV/decade)	19.9 ± 0.3	19.9 ± 0.3	19.7 ± 0.2	19.6 ± 0.2	19.7 ± 0.3	19.5 ± 0.3	19.8 ± 0.3
$\log K_{\text{sel}} > -2$	Lu, La, Yb	-	Na, Mg, Sm, Pb, Dy, Gd	Dy, Sm, Er, Na, Pb	Dy, Tb, Pb	Sm, Dy, Cu	-

Fig. 5. Potentiometric titration curve of 20.0 mL from a 1.0×10^{-4} M Ho^{3+} solution with 1.0×10^{-2} M of EDTA.

Table 4. Determination of fluoride ions in mouth wash solutions

Sample	Labeled (mg/mL)	Found ISE ^a (mg/mL)
Sodium fluoride mouth wash solution (Aquafresh, Brentford, UK)	1.35	$(1.37 \pm 0.03)^b$
Sodium fluoride mouth wash solution (Eurodont, DuroDont GmbH)	1.45	(1.48 ± 0.05)

^aSuggested Ho^{3+} sensor.

^bResults are based on three measurements.

Table 5. Determination of Ho^{3+} spiked in tap and river water samples by use of the proposed electrode

Sample	Ho^{3+} added (mg/mL)	Found (mg/mL)	Recovery (%)
River water	0.25	$(0.27^a \pm 0.03)$	108
	0.5	(0.53 ± 0.02)	106
Tap water	0.25	(0.28 ± 0.04)	112
	0.5	(0.54 ± 0.03)	108

^aResults are based on three measurements.

titrated with a Ho^{3+} solution (1.0×10^{-3} M). And the results of triplicate measurements are summarized in Table 4. As seen there is a satisfactory agreement among the declared fluoride content and the values determined by the proposed sensor.

The proposed sensor was also applied to the direct determination of holmium ions in different water samples and the results of triplicate measurements are given in Table 5. As can be seen, the accuracy of holmium determination in different water samples is almost quantitative.

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